

Deriving Equation for the Viscosity Increase of Sols of Polyacrylic Acids During Alkalimetric Titration

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Combining Smoluchowski's electroviscous equation with the author's equation* to account for the variation of specific conductivity of colloidal electrolytes with dilution the following equation has been deduced

$$R = 1 + \frac{m(\alpha - \alpha_0)}{m_0 + (\alpha - \alpha_0)}$$

where R represents the ratio of the specific viscosity of the polyacrylic acid sol to which some alkali has been added and α its degree of dissociation to that of the sol to which no alkali has been added and its degree of dissociation is α_0 and m and m_0 are constants.

In the case of polyacrylic acid sol values of R calculated by using this equation agree well with those observed when α is varied from 0.038 to 0.80.

In the case of polymethacrylic acid sols values of R calculated by using this equation upto $\alpha=0.1$ and above $\alpha=0.34$ agree well with those observed provided m is given a separate value for each of these two ranges of α . The value of m upto $\alpha=0.1$ is smaller than that above $\alpha=0.34$. It has been shown on the basis of the arguments used in the deduction of the equation that the increase of m between $\alpha=0.1$ and $\alpha=0.34$ is caused by the transformation of the macromolecules of polymethacrylic acid from the folded to the unfolded form.

THE variations of pH and viscosity of sols of polyacrylic acid (PAA) and polymethacrylic acid (PMA) with the increase in the degree of dissociation α during titration by an alkali have been investigated by several authors¹⁻⁶. Such investigations²⁻⁶ have revealed that as α increases during neutralisation, the macromolecules of PMA undergo transformation from the folded to the unfolded form†, while no such change has been detected in the case of PAA^{4,6}. The equations so far deduced²⁻³ to account for the increase in specific viscosity with the increase of α , caused by neutralisation, agree only qualitatively with the experimental data.

In this paper it will be shown that by suitably modifying Smoluchowski's equation, it is possible to deduce an equation which holds for the specific viscosity increase of PAA over a wide range of α and also for the specific viscosity increase of PMA over such values of α in which its macromolecules exist either in the folded or the unfolded form. During the transformation from the folded to the unfolded form one of the two constants in the equation changes.

Derivation of the equation :

In a previous publication⁷ it has been shown that by combining Smoluchowski's electroviscous equation⁸ with an equation derived by the author to account for the variation of specific conductivity of colloidal electrolytes with dilution the following equation is obtained

$$\eta_{sp} = K\phi \left[1 + \frac{(C + K_0)}{\eta_0 r^2 (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1)} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_{sp} represents the specific viscosity of the sol, K, according to Einstein, is a constant [equal to 2.5 for spherical particles], ϕ the volume fraction, r the radius and ζ the electrokinetic potential of the colloidal particles, C their concentration (unit arbitrary) and K_0 a constant, λ_s the specific conductivity per unit area of the plane of contact of the diffuse electrical double layer (of the colloidal particles) with an electrode of the conductivity cell, λ_1 the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution, D and η_0 are the dielectric constant and viscosity of the dispersion medium.

* The author's equation is based on the assumption that the specific conductivity of a colloidal electrolyte solution is made up of two parts, one part contributed by the colloidal particles and the small ions present in the diffuse double layers and the other part contributed by the small ions present in the intermicellar solution.

† The author prefers to use the terms folded and unfolded instead of helix and coil which are often used.

In a carefully dialysed sol λ_1 is very small and its change during neutralisation may be neglected, but each of the factors ζ , r and λ_s increases with progressive neutralisation. Let the value of these quantities for $\alpha = \alpha_0$ be denoted by ζ , r and λ_s then their value as α increases may be represented by $\zeta[1+b(\alpha-\alpha_0)]$, $r[1+g(\alpha-\alpha_0)]$ and $\lambda_s[1+h(\alpha-\alpha_0)]$ respectively where b , g and h are the corresponding coefficients of increment and α_0 the degree of dissociation to start with. Substituting these values in equation (1), neglecting† such terms as $bg(\alpha-\alpha_0)^2$, $b(\alpha-\alpha_0)^2$, and $g(\alpha-\alpha_0)^2$ & which are small compared to the other quantities and putting $(\alpha-\alpha_0) = a$, equation (1) may be written as follows :

$$(\eta_{sp})_\alpha = K\phi \left[1 + \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \frac{(K_0 + C)\{1 + 2(b-g)a\}}{\eta_0 r^2 \{C\lambda_s(1+ha) + K_0\lambda_1\}} \right] \dots (2)$$

where $(\eta_{sp})_\alpha$ represents the specific viscosity of the sol when the degree of neutralisation is α .

Denoting specific viscosity of the sol for which $\alpha = \alpha_0$ by $(\eta_{sp})_0$ the ratio of $(\eta_{sp})_\alpha : (\eta_{sp})_0$ by R , putting $H = (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1)$ and $B = (H + A\zeta^2)$ and

$$A = \left(\frac{D}{2\pi} \right)^2 \frac{(K_0 + C)}{\eta_0 r^2}$$

it follows from the equations (1) and (2) that

$$R = \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2\{1 + 2(b-g)a\}}{H + C\lambda_s ha} \right] : \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2}{H} \right] \dots (3)$$

$$= \left[\frac{1 + 2A\zeta^2(b-g)a/B + (C\lambda_s ha/B)}{1 + C ha/H} \right]$$

$$= \left[1 + \frac{1 + 2A\zeta^2(b-g)a/B + (C\lambda_s ha/B) - 1 - (C\lambda_s ha/H)}{\frac{C\lambda_s h}{H} \left(\frac{H}{C\lambda_s h} + a \right)} \right] \dots (3a)$$

$$= 1 + \frac{m(\alpha - \alpha_0)}{m_0 + (\alpha - \alpha_0)} \dots (4)$$

where $m = \left[\frac{2A\zeta^2(b-g) + C\lambda_s h}{B} - \frac{C\lambda_s h}{H} \right] / \frac{C\lambda_s h}{H}$

and $m_0 = \frac{H}{C\lambda_s h} = \frac{C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1}{C\lambda_s h}$

At a constant concentration of the colloidal acid and that of the added neutral salt, m and m_0 in equation (4) should remain constant, when α is varied, provided each of the three coefficients, b , g and h remains constant, since all the other terms involved have fixed values. Of the three coefficients, b and h are expected to remain constant as α is varied from its initial value to about 0.7 or 0.8, but g , the coefficient of increment of the radius r , may remain constant only up to a certain value of α , say α_1 (much smaller than 0.2) and after that it may change and finally diminish approaching zero or a small constant value. This change in g should occur in polyacids the macromolecules of which exist in

the folded form when α is small and undergo transformation into the unfolded form when α increases beyond α_1 . After the macromolecules have changed into the unfolded form, they either cease to expand any more or expand only slightly. Therefore, g becomes either zero or very small when the transformation of the macromolecules into the unfolded form is complete. Consequently m in equation (4) should change during the transformation and become constant after the transformation has occurred.

The data recorded in the Tables 1 to 3 will show how far the values of R calculated by using equation (4) agree with those observed.

TABLE 1—DATA ON VISCOSITY AND TITRATION OF POLYACRYLIC ACID AT 20°

Miscellaneous	pH	α	η_{sp}/C	m	Observed R	Calculated R
D.P.—340	2.95	0.018	13.0	12.0	0.49	0.50
G=0.0625 eqv./L	3.12	0.020	15.4	12.0	0.59	0.55
$\alpha_0=0.038$	3.28	0.025	18.6	12.0	0.71	0.68
$m_0=0.50$	3.46	0.038	26.3	14.4	1.00	1.00
	3.84	0.066	45.6	14.4	1.78	1.76
	4.36	0.130	85.3	14.4	3.24	3.24
	5.13	0.256	150.0	14.4	5.70	5.37
	6.24	0.512	219.0	14.4	8.93	8.01
	6.71	0.640	233.0	14.4	8.86	8.88
	7.48	0.800	247.0	14.4	9.39	9.69

TABLE 2—DATA ON VISCOSITY AND TITRATION OF PMA SAMPLE II B AT 25°

Miscellaneous	pH	α	η_{sp}	m	Observed R	Calculated R
KCl—0.0001 N	3.72	0.020	0.031	25.0	1.00	1.00
M—139000	4.16	0.028	0.055	25.0	1.77	1.78
G=0.0099 eqv./L	4.65	0.044	0.086	25.0	2.77	3.20
$\alpha_0=0.02$	5.44	0.053	0.186	25.0	6.00	6.03
$m_0=0.25$	5.95	0.155	0.403	34.2	13.0	13.0
	6.54	0.343	1.119	62.0	36.1	36.0
	7.22	0.520	1.399	62.0	43.2	42.3
	7.96	0.728	1.453	62.0	46.0	46.8
KCl—0.001 N	3.74	0.019	0.021	16.5	1.00	1.00
M—139000	4.16	0.028	0.030	16.5	1.42	1.50
G=0.0099 eqv./L	4.60	0.044	0.046	16.5	2.27	2.31
$\alpha_0=0.019$	5.35	0.083	0.093	16.5	4.43	3.98
$m_0=0.29$	5.91	0.155	0.200	26.7	9.52	9.52
	6.52	0.343	0.727	65.0	34.5	35.3
	7.21	0.520	0.891	65.0	42.4	42.2
	7.95	0.728	0.980	65.0	46.7	46.1
KCl—0.01 N	3.65	0.025	0.016	6.1	1.00	1.00
M—139000	4.12	0.040	0.018	6.1	1.13	1.16
G=0.0099 eqv./L	4.60	0.065	0.023	6.1	1.44	1.42
$\alpha_0=0.025$	5.45	0.156	0.046	9.7	2.88	2.88
$m_0=0.54$	6.05	0.343	0.221	35.2	13.8	14.00
	6.68	0.520	0.299	35.2	18.7	17.80
	7.44	0.728	0.334	35.2	20.9	20.9

† Neglecting $(\alpha - \alpha_0)^2$ and higher order terms.

TABLE 3—DATA ON VISCOSITY AND TITRATION OF PMA SAMPLE II A AT 25°

Miscellaneous	pH	α	η_{sp}	m	Observed R	Calculated R
KCl—0.001 N	3.81	0.016	0.051	19.0	1.00	1.00
M—266000	4.22	0.027	0.084	19.0	1.65	1.90
C=0.0101 eqv./L	4.81	0.042	0.155	19.0	3.04	3.01
$\alpha_0=0.016$	5.47	0.092	0.278	19.0	5.45	5.40
$m_0=0.22$	5.93	0.153	0.589	27.5	11.6	11.60
KCl—0.01 N	3.67	0.023	0.034	12.5	1.00	1.00
M—266000	3.97	0.032	0.040	12.5	1.18	1.16
C=0.0101 eqv./L	4.28	0.046	0.047	12.5	1.38	1.40
$\alpha_0=0.023$	4.85	0.083	0.068	12.5	2.00	2.00
$m_0=0.69$	5.50	0.153	0.105	13.2	3.09	3.09
	6.07	0.336	0.536	46.4	15.5	15.50
	6.68	0.509	0.739	46.4	21.7	20.2
	7.42	0.714	0.821	46.4	24.2	24.2

The specific viscosity η_{sp} of the sols of PAA of degree of polymerisation (D.P.) 340 and "grund molarity" 0.0625 has been determined by Kern¹ during their neutralisation by NaOH at 25°. The data taken from Table 4 of his paper are recorded in Table 1. Under the head miscellaneous in column 1 of the table, C represents "grund molarity" i.e. 72 grams of the acid per liter of the solution and α_0 and m_0 have the same significance as stated already.

The specific viscosity of the sols of PMA having different molecular weight and KCl concentration has been determined by Arnold and Overbeek² during neutralisation by NaOH at 25°. Their data on the samples II A and II B of the PMA sols which have been carefully purified and dialysed are recorded in the Tables 2 and 3. Under the head miscellaneous of the aforesaid tables, M represents the molecular weight of the acid, C, its concentration in equivalents per liter, the KCl concentration is expressed in moles per liter and the other terms have same significance as stated already.

Discussion

It may be mentioned that $(K\phi)$ in equation (1) has been treated as a constant in the deduction of equation (4). It is probable that during titration, specially when the transformation from the folded to the unfolded form occurs, $(K\phi)$ changes. Let us assume that the change occurs according to the equation $(K\phi) = (K\phi)_1 (1 + Aa)$ where $(K\phi)_1$ is the initial value of $(K\phi)$, A is the coefficient of increment, and as stated already $a = (\alpha - \alpha_0)$. To include this change in equation (4) its right hand side should be multiplied by $(1 + Aa)$. It may then be written as follows :

$$R = \left[1 + \frac{m_1 a}{m_0 + a} \right] (1 + Aa) \quad \dots (4a)$$

Simplifying equation (4a) and neglecting terms involving a^2 , we get the following equation :

$$R = \left[1 + \frac{(m_1 + m_0 A)(\alpha - \alpha_0)}{m_0 + (\alpha - \alpha_0)} \right] \\ = \left[1 + \frac{m(\alpha - \alpha_0)}{m_0 + (\alpha - \alpha_0)} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

Where $m = (m_1 + m_0 A)$

Therefore, m should change when A and m_1 change, either singly or jointly.

Kern¹ has noticed that upto $\alpha = 0.038$ the specific conductivity of the PAA sol decreased slowly and thereafter it increased steadily upto $\alpha = 0.80$ where the titration was stopped. Therefore, 0.038 has been taken as α_0 in equation (5), and it has been used as ; $R = \left[1 + \frac{m(\alpha - 0.038)}{m_0 + (\alpha - 0.038)} \right]$

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that above $\alpha = 0.038$ taking $m_0 = 0.50$ and $m = 14.4$ the values of R calculated by using equation (5) agree well with those observed upto the end. Again below $\alpha = 0.038$ keeping m_0 the same i.e. 0.50 and taking $m = 12.0$ the calculated values of R agree well with those observed. The slightly low value of m below $\alpha = 0.038$ may be taken as an indication that the macromolecules of PAA are a bit more compact in this region of α than that above it.

From the data recorded in the Tables 2 and 3, where equation (5) has been used in its usual form, it will be noticed that at a given concentration of KCl, m_0 remains constant, but m has got a fixed value upto about $\alpha = 0.1$, thereafter, it increases and again attains a fixed value as α increases above 0.34. In each of these ranges of α the values of R calculated by using equation (5) agree well with those observed.

As m changes between $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.34$ it is to be concluded, on the basis of the arguments used in the derivation of equation (5), that the transformation of the macromolecules of PMA from the folded to the unfolded form occurs within this range of α . This conclusion is in agreement with the observations of the previous authors²⁻⁶.

The data also show that as the concentration of KCl is increased, m_0 in equation (5) increases. Such an increase of m_0 follows from the relation $m_0 = (C\lambda_s + K_0\lambda_1)/C\lambda_s h$, where λ_1 increases nearly proportionately with the KCl concentration while the other terms change only to a small extent.

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